

NIGHT SKY TOURISM: A QUICK START GUIDE WORKBOOK

FOR INHABITANTS OF RURAL AREAS

Night sky tourism is any tourism activity that happens **outdoors at night**. This workbook is designed to help you come up with an interesting and locally relevant night sky activity that will attract guests to your area and stimulate the local economy.

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For more resources and support, visit
www.astrotourism.astro4dev.org or
email astrotourism@astro4dev.org

1. CHOOSING A NIGHTTIME ACTIVITY

Pick **ONE** idea from these, or use them as inspiration to come up with your own idea for an experience at night. This idea will form the core of the experience.

When you're choosing this idea, keep in mind what is available to you and the location you plan to offer this activity in. Choose something that you already have the skills and resources for.

LOCAL FOOD

A traditional meal under the stars

Teaching people how to prepare food over fire

Food tasting of local items in the dark (wine, honey, fruits, etc.)

Nighttime picnic

TIP: Try to find an activity that would also work indoors or in a sheltered setting in case of bad weather.

CULTURAL PERFORMANCES

Singing or music performances in the dark

Traditional dances by a fire

Cultural storytelling under the stars

Darkness sound therapy

Yoga under the stars

Guided meditation in the dark

WELLNESS & MINDFULNESS

ART

Painting by the fire

Dyeing textiles by a fire

Making local crafts by a fire

NIGHTTIME WALKS

Nighttime village walking tours

Wildlife walks: listening for the sounds of different animals

The activity you select will serve as the core of your night sky tourism experience. Whether you choose from the options in the Quick Start Guide or use these as inspiration to craft your own, remember to align it with the available resources and skills in your community.

SELECTING YOUR ACTIVITY

Choose ONE activity from the list on the previous page, or let them inspire your own idea.

RESOURCE ASSESSMENT

List the skills and talents present in your community.

examples: artisans, storytellers, culinary experts, musicians or performers, agricultural knowledge, nature enthusiasts

Identify resources available for the selected activity.

examples: local crafts and art supplies, local stories/myths/legends, local ingredients, musical instruments, performance spaces, agricultural produce, information about plants/animals, walking trails or open spaces, community expertise

Note any potential challenges and how to address them.

Examples: If a challenge is limited artisan availability, you can collaborate with artisans by scheduling activities during weekends or community holidays. If a challenge is insufficient information on local plants and animals, consult local experts, collaborate with environmental organisations, or stick to providing basic information

2. HOW CAN YOU USE LOCALLY MADE CRAFTS AND OBJECTS IN YOUR ACTIVITY?

Try to incorporate as many local crafts and cultural objects into your experience as you can. These cultural touchpoints will add authenticity to your experience. They can also be sold to guests at the end of the experience (make sure you sell them new items, not the ones they have used). Consider the following examples, or any other local crafts and objects that you can think of that can be used in your experience.

POTTERY

Plates

Bowls

Cups and mugs

BASKETRY

Baskets

Bags

Woven mats

TEXTILES

Scarves and shawls

Blankets

Carpets

Napkins

Clothing items

BEADWORK

Using beads to accessorise other items

Jewellery

TIP: Use as many different cultural crafts and objects that you can think of in your chosen activity.

example: for a 'dinner under the stars' experience, use plates, mugs and bowls made by a local potter, napkins with local prints, and provide locally woven shawls for people to keep warm while eating outdoors.

ACTIVITY DESIGN & CULTURAL ELEMENTS

SETTING

Describe the ideal location for your activity.

MATERIALS

What essentials do you need? Think blankets, local snacks, crafts, or any specific items related to your activity.

TIMING

What are the best times to start and end your experience? Consider sunset, darkness, and local schedules.

ARRIVAL AND WELCOME

How will you greet participants? What's the first impression you want them to have?

ACTIVITY SETUP

How will you arrange the space? Think about seating, decor, or any elements that enhance the ambiance.

MAIN SESSION

What is the focus of the activity and the core message you want to communicate? How can you ensure this comes across?

ENGAGEMENT

How will you keep participants engaged? Consider discussions, interactions, or hands-on elements.

CLOSING

Conclude your activity with a memorable moment. Reflect on the experience and offer any follow-up actions.

CULTURAL INTEGRATION

Make a list of all the physical objects you will need for your experience.

For as many of these objects as you can, try to figure out how you can use traditional crafts, locally made items, or items decorated with local motifs and symbols. Feel free to get creative with the resources available to you.

Identify local artisans or craftspeople to collaborate with in making these items, or where you can source them.

Plan how new versions of these items can also be sold to guests at the end of the experience. Will they be available in a shop, or will you advertise and sell them yourself at the end of the experience?

3. CULTURAL ASTRONOMY

Every culture in history has developed a unique relationship with objects in the night sky. Here are some aspects of your own cultural astronomy to research and include in your night sky experience. You might know some of these stories yourself, or you can reach out to family and community members or cultural experts to find out more. You can also reach out to your country's [IAU National Outreach Coordinator](#) to ask for help with finding this information.

THE SUN AND MOON

The Sun and Moon sometimes represent Gods or deities, or are believed to influence human and animal behaviour. Here are some cultural perspectives of the Sun and Moon that you can look into.

The surface
of the Moon

Phases of
the Moon

Lunar
calendars

Are there any stories, myths, or practical applications of the Sun and Moon that occur in your culture?

SPECIAL EVENTS

Some special events can be culturally interpreted as good or bad omens, or have certain rituals or beliefs surrounding them.

Meteor showers

Eclipses

TIP: Find perspectives of the night sky that are unique to your culture. This will make your night sky experience unique and attractive to visitors.

What are the beliefs around special events in the night sky in your culture?

STARS AND CONSTELLATIONS

Stars and constellations are often used for orientation, navigation and timekeeping. They may also be believed to be linked to personal and community fortunes. Here are some cultural perspectives of stars and constellations that you can look into.

Navigation and
finding directions

Farming and
agriculture

Timing rituals,
festivals, holy
months, or
other events

Astrology

Star/sidereal
calendars

What are the beliefs around specific stars and constellations in your culture? Do you use them for farming, or to time rituals and festivals? If you follow a specific cultural calendar, do some research into how this calendar is linked to the night sky.

BELIEFS AROUND NIGHTTIME

Does your culture have any beliefs, stories, or myths about nighttime in general? Which of these can you include in your experience?

4. THE LOGISTICS OF THE ACTIVITY

LOCATION

Here are some important things to keep in mind when you are choosing where to carry out your activity. Tick the checkboxes for every question you answer yes to - the aim should be to tick all of them.

Safety Measures

Make sure your locations are safe from people and wild animals

- Is the location safe from potential risks like tripping hazards or uneven terrain?
- Is the location safe from people and wild animals at night? Make a note of any extra measures you can take to increase the safety of the location.
- Is there enough visibility at night for people to move around safely?

Permission and Approvals

Obtain proper permission to use the locations from the people who own them

- Do you have the permission to use the location from the property owners/relevant authorities?
- Do you have permission from local people or property owners to host your event?
- Have you looked into and taken care of any paperwork or approvals needed?

Backup Location for Weather

Choose a back-up indoor location in case of bad weather

- Do you have a backup location in case of bad weather?
- Does the backup location satisfy the checklist criteria above?

Access to Facilities

Make sure people have access to bathrooms before or during the experience

- Can your guests access bathrooms before, during, or after the activity?
- Have you made this clear to them in your communication?

Legal Compliance

Make sure you obtain the proper licenses and approvals for your activities

- Do you have the proper permits, licenses, and approvals for your activity?

ACCESSIBILITY

These are questions that will help clarify guests' expectations of the activity, and make sure they are prepared. Make sure you have clear answers to each of these prompts, and communicate them with guests in advance.

What can you do to accommodate people with disabilities?

Will you provide food and beverages during the activity?

Is the activity pet-friendly?

Is the activity child-friendly?

Will you provide any special clothing or equipment needed, or do they bring it?

Will you provide transportation to/from the activity?

BEFORE THE EXPERIENCE

Make sure you let guests know what to expect, and prepare for emergency situations.

Brief guests about what to expect and what to bring with them

Refer to the previous page, and provide as much detail as possible to help them feel prepared.

First Aid Kit

Buy or put together a basic first aid kit, and learn how to use it in case of an emergency.

A plan for what to do in case of emergencies

Identify emergency situations, including medical emergencies, weather-related issues, equipment malfunctions, unexpected wildlife encounters, lost participants: public disturbances, and transportation issues. There may be others unique to your situation - make a note of them.

For each scenario, outline simple and clear steps to ensure participant safety, including communication, evacuation, and first aid measures.

Using the example below, draft an emergency plan for emergency situations you might encounter

EXAMPLE:

Type of emergency

Medical Emergency

Action Steps

Designate a first aid kit with basic medical supplies.
Train staff in basic first aid and CPR.
Establish clear communication channels to promptly alert emergency services.

EMERGENCY PLAN

Type of emergency

Action Steps

PRICING Set a profitable and affordable price.

Find a price that allows you to make a profit

COST ANALYSIS

List all the costs associated with organizing and conducting the astrotourism activity. Include expenses such as equipment, permits, and any amenities provided.

Make sure your price is aligned with other similar experiences

MARKET RESEARCH

What are the prices of similar experiences in your region (even if they happen during the day)? What are the unique aspects of your activity that may justify a premium or discounted price?

VALUE PROPOSITION

Clearly communicate the value participants will receive for the price. Highlight unique aspects that set your astrotourism experience apart.

5. TEST RUN

Test out your activity from start to finish on friends and family. Ask them for feedback and note down what they say can be improved. Did everything go according to plan, or were there things you hadn't thought of? Make a note to accommodate these.

Pre-Event Setup

- Prepare all necessary equipment, props, and materials as if it were the actual event
- Verify that safety measures and emergency protocols are in place

Simulate Participant Arrival

- Carry out the participant arrival process, from check-in to any welcome activities
- Assess the clarity of directions and the efficiency of the check-in process

NOTES:

Activity Execution

- Lead friends and family through the entire astrotourism experience
- Pay attention to pacing, engagement levels, and the overall flow of activities
- Make notes of what could be improved

NOTES:

Feedback Collection

- Pause often throughout the experience to gather feedback from participants
- Make notes of what they say works and what doesn't work

NOTES:

Revised Run-through

- Implement the changes and conduct a second run-through
- Did the changes enhance the experience and make things go more smoothly? Take notes.

NOTES:

6. EXTRA TIPS

ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

Responsible nighttime tourism involves protecting the environment that the experience happens in. Following these tips should help you prevent environmental damage.

Do not litter or leave trash at the activity location

If your activity generates waste, how can you make sure this is disposed in the recommended way?

Limit the number of people who can participate to avoid excessive damage to the environment

What is the minimum number of participants you can accommodate at a reasonable profit?

Do not make unnecessary noise

Brief participants beforehand to talk at a low volume and keep disruption to the environment low

Limit or completely avoid using single-use plastic items

What single-use plastic items can you replace with other items?

PROTECTING THE NIGHT SKY

Since night sky tourism is greatly enhanced by a good view of the moon and stars, using light responsibly and in low amounts helps to maximise the number of stars visible. Responsible lighting also reduces health impacts on people and nocturnal animals. Here are some easy to implement tips for sustainable outdoor lighting for your activity.

Turn off as many outdoor lights as possible

Try to limit your use of artificial light to candles and firelight

Where electric light is needed, use red light instead of white/yellow

Shield outdoor lights to reduce glare

DarkSky International is the authority on responsible outdoor lighting to help reduce light pollution. You can implement their Five Principles for Responsible Outdoor Lighting by working through the following questions:

Five Lighting Principles for Responsible Outdoor Lighting

Responsible outdoor lighting is	1 Useful	<p>Use light only if it is needed</p> <p>All light should have a clear purpose. Consider how the use of light will impact the area, including wildlife and their habitats.</p>	
	2 Targeted	<p>Direct light so it falls only where it is needed</p> <p>Use shielding and careful aiming to target the direction of the light beam so that it points downward and does not spill beyond where it is needed.</p>	
	3 Low Level	<p>Light should be no brighter than necessary</p> <p>Use the lowest light level required. Be mindful of surface conditions, as some surfaces may reflect more light into the night sky than intended.</p>	
	4 Controlled	<p>Use light only when it is needed</p> <p>Use controls such as timers or motion detectors to ensure that light is available when it is needed, dimmed when possible, and turned off when not needed.</p>	
	5 Warm-colored	<p>Use warmer color lights where possible</p> <p>Limit the amount of shorter wavelength (blue-violet) light to the least amount needed.</p>	

image source: darksky.org

7. SPREADING THE WORD

MARKETING & PROMOTION

Marketing is key to reaching a wider audience and ensuring your night sky experience gets the attention it deserves.

TIP: Get some high quality images of your experience as it's happening, and use these to market the experience. Hire a professional photographer if you have the budget for it.

Use social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and X/Twitter to showcase your experience

Set up a booth at local community events to distribute flyers and engage with potential participants

Reach out to local newspapers, magazines, and influential bloggers for coverage

Develop a simple website or blog to provide detailed information about your night sky experience

Build an email list of interested participants and send regular updates about upcoming events, special promotions, or exclusive offers

Encourage participants to share their experiences with friends and family. Consider implementing a referral program

Partner with local businesses, such as restaurants, cafes, or hotels to cross-promote your experience. Offer package deals or discounts to their customers

Reach out to local and regional tourism agencies to include your experience in their promotional materials

PLATFORMS TO SHOWCASE YOUR EXPERIENCE

AirBnB Experiences

Viator

EventBrite

Facebook Events

Travel Forums & Communities

8. NEXT STEPS

If you would like to develop this idea further and work towards developing a business plan, please refer to our resource **Night Sky Tourism for Communities around Observatories**. While that resource is targeted at observatories and support organisations, you can make use of the Business Model Canvas idea in it to develop and clarify yours further. Section 3 of the resource contains guidelines to creating a Business Model Canvas, and a sample Business Model Canvas for experiences that you can use to develop your own.

For more resources and support, visit astro4dev.org, or email us at astrotourism@astro4dev.org.

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